

Geospatial Analysis of Petroleum Retail Outlets in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State

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Abstract

In an economy whose principal source of energy is fossil fuel, there is bound to be an influx of several downstream activities including the proliferation of Petroleum Retail Outlets (PRO) or filling stations. This study assessed a geospatial analysis of PRO in the city of Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State. Garmin GPSMAP® 64st handheld Global Positioning Systems (GPS) receivers were used in taking the spatial coordinates of PRO, while simple random technique was utilized in administering semi-structured questionnaires to 200 respondents in residential buildings located 100m from PRO. Descriptive statistics and GIS were used in data analyses and presentations. The results showed that majority of the mapped PRO violated the DPR locational standard of not more than 4 PRO within 2km radius while noise pollution in residential areas, air pollution in the houses close-by as well as traffic in the filling station spilling to residential areas were most perceived environmental problems associated with proliferation of PRO in the area. The study recommends appropriate sanctions upon PRO operators/owners who have violated the DPR rules. These may range from withdrawal of operational license, stiffer financial fines, closure and/relocation among others. Also, geospatial technologies should be deployed in assessment of spatial phenomena based on its capabilities in supporting policies and in making informed decisions.

Keywords: *Petroleum Retail Outlets (PRO), Geographic Information System (GIS), Remote Sensing (RS), Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR).*

Introduction

Over the years, economic geographers among other issues have deployed several techniques to analyse obvious economic problems including indiscriminate location of petroleum retail outlets (PRO). One of such techniques is geospatial technologies. According to Dempsey (2014), “the word geospatial is used to denote a collection of data and associated technology”. But for a data to be termed “geospatial”, “information about a particular phenomenon has to be well organized in order to understand how locational attributes vary in space” (Torbick *et al.*, 2014). Geospatial analysis is therefore “the application of geographic information systems (GIS), remote sensing (RS) and global positioning systems (GPS) in evaluation spatial phenomenon in time and space” (Cimons, 2011).

Nevertheless, the expansion of technology in the automobile industry has had a significant impact in the petroleum industry which has triggered the building of several petrol filling stations otherwise referred to as petroleum retail outlets (PRO) at strategic locations to meet the demand of vehicular operations (Abdul *et al.*, 2009; Tah, 2017). The significant roles petroleum products play in any economy are well

Article History:

Received: 28.08.2025

Revised: 12.09.2025

Accepted: 26.09.2025

Published: 02.10.2025

Citation: Oluku, S., & Wuka, B.B. (2025). Geospatial Analysis of Petroleum Retail Outlets in Yenagoa Metropolis, Bayelsa State. *European Journal of Science and Modern Technologies*, 1(5), 41-53. [https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1\(5\).05](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejsmt.2025.1(5).05)

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known. Chinambu (2012) acknowledged that, petroleum is a key driver of industrial activities (Tah, 2017). Besides the industrial development, the transportation sector is presumed to be the major consumer of fuel to facilitate mankind's movement patterns around the globe (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016; Tah, 2017).

Chinambu (2012) stressed that, retail gasoline is one of the most analyzed products in the world because of people's reliance on cars. However, the price dynamics and its effects on economies of both developed and developing worlds have also been documented. (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016) In the case of price dynamics, it has been documented that there are significant ripple effects on most developing economies due to a rise in a barrel of crude oil. Sidaway (1998) stated that, petrol stations are very vulnerable to closures resulting from petrol price competition, regulatory pressure and nonstrategic locations. (James, & Obi, 2020) Mudambi (1994) supported Sidaway when he stated that, location affects many aspects of petrol station operation. The dark side of petroleum (especially, fuel for refueling vehicles) is the environmental effects on the eco-system hence its service location points must be strategically and consciously sited to minimize it on both humans and their immediate environment. (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016). For instance, in the Scandinavian countries particularly in Finland and Sweden, efforts have been made to remedy the effects of pollutants on air, water and soil within abandoned petrol filling sites (Nieminen, 2005; Taiwo, 2018). According to Mshelia *et al*, (2015), it has been discovered that PRO are located close to residential areas and in some cases close to commercial and industrial activities (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016).

As the population increases, so does the number of automobiles, thereby creating the need for fueling services and consequently the construction of petrol filling stations. Hanekom, (2001); Genovese, (2004) and Spencer, (2004) are of the view that petrol station or PRO could be any petroleum facility, service station, public garage, highway filling station, petrol part or fuel depot that sells fuel and lubricants for motor vehicles (Mshelia, John, & Emmanuel, 2015). Even though this facility may have different names depending on the part of the world, the purpose to which it is located still remains the same (Mshelia, John, & Emmanuel, 2015). That is, a structure or building where petroleum products are sold to motorists or for other local consumption. For instance, in Australia the facility is called service station; in Canada, it is either garage, fueling station or gas bar; in some English speaking Common Wealth Countries it is also either petrol station or petrol pump; in India, petrol bunk; in Japanese English, gasoline; in Nigeria, filling station; in UK and South Africa, garage and in USA it is known as gas station (Mshelia, John, & Emmanuel, 2015).

A petroleum retail outlet/service station by definition is a public facility, where fuel (petrol, kerosene, diesel etc.) and lubricants for automobiles are sold to end users. Most of these PRO sell petrol, diesel and kerosene. And these fuels contain high concentration of hazardous substance that causes huge damage to human's life and the proliferation of fuel service stations is now a current trend in most of our urban areas (Samuel *et al*, 2015; Ogunyemi, et al., 2017). Filling Station otherwise known as Petrol station, Gas Station, Refueling Station, or PRO across the world is a facility which sells fuel and lubricants for motor vehicles, generators and other machine. The most common fuel products sold is Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) known as petrol, Automotive Gas Oil (AGO) and Dual Purpose Kerosene (DPK) known as kerosene, Keeble (1968) in Samuel (2011) (Ogunyemi, et al., 2017). According to the Collins English Dictionary, a PRO is a place where you can buy petrol and oil for your vehicle; it is also a place where petrol and other supplies for motorists are sold. Most filling stations sell petrol or diesel, some carry specialty fuels such as liquefied petroleum gas (LPG), natural gas, hydrogen, biodiesel, kerosene, or butane while the rest add shops to their primary business (Hamid *et al*, 2009; Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016). Similarly, Nieminen (2005) defined Petrol station as an area including fuel equipment and piping, storage tanks, forecourt and possible building premises for the sale of fuel (inflammable liquids) to customer's vehicles (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016).

In recent times, there has been a sustained increase in the number of PRO established in different parts of the country (Tah, 2017). The reasons for such unprecedented increase are not far-fetched. Firstly, the increasing population in the country and the attendant increase in the purchase of vehicle; Secondly, the attractive price of petrol both at control price and black market price which made more people to go into petrol retailing business (Uchegbu, 2002; Tah, 2017). The rapid growth of vehicular traffic in the country and subsequent increase in the number of petrol filling stations along the motor-ways and also in towns and city roads as well as within settlements urges for a real need to control and manage the development of such activities (Njoku, & Alagbe, 2015). The rise in global population has outpaced and is posing serious challenges on the government to provide the masses with the essential infrastructure as well as enact and enforce legislations on the people (WHO, 2010; Njoku, & Alagbe, 2015).

Nigeria is a blessed nation or country with abundant natural resources of which petroleum products play a vital role in Nigeria's economy (CBN, 2010; Mohammed, Musa, & Jeb, 2014). This petroleum products account for 78% of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and also account for 90% of the Nigeria's total annual revenue and foreign exchange earnings (NBS, 2008; Mohammed, Musa, & Jeb, 2014).

In Nigeria, PRO operations started prior to independence; the production and distribution of petroleum products which did not gain much popularity until independence in 1960 as a result of the fact that the mileage of motor able roads rarely increased and have few vehicles plying these roads. However, with the independence in 1960, construction of more roads, schools, and factories started and consumption of petroleum products increased. Demands for all grades of petroleum products started to overtake the supply and this became more manifested after the civil war leading to opening of many filling stations across the country (Abdul *et al.*, 2009).

Selecting a better site for business enterprise is at the mind of every government and entrepreneur who invest their capital to earn profit (Taiwo, 2018). Some of the variables considered when selecting location for utility are proximity to population centres, distance from neighboring stations, the easements of using existing utility, and the magnitudes of environmental pollution parameters (Abdul *et al.*, 2009; Taiwo, 2018). Other factors to take into account when making a decision about the location of business, including customers, transport, the neighbourhood, finances and the longer term future (Abdul *et al.*, 2009; Taiwo, 2018).

One of the purpose that necessitates the establishment of a PRO is to promote and enhance the availability of fuels such as petrol, kerosene, diesel and gas etc. to consumers, at all times; in order to achieve this, their services and operations in relation to their consumers, has to be optimally distributed and efficiently managed so as to achieve maximum results. Good access to quality PRO is important for motorists in any location; most car owners in the city have their own idea of which filling stations are best to get fuel in terms of distances and their quality. However, the issue of PRO can be analyzed from the perspective of spatial location, economic, environment, as well as road safety. In some locality, the establishment of filling station impacts both positively and negatively to the environment as well as human lives which has shown that the impact of PRO on the city environment as well as human health is a pressing question.

With the large number of registered cars and PRO in urban areas, the problems of the distribution, the location and the sitting of PRO need careful examination with regard to the control that requires to be exercised; the legislation instruments that may be required to enforce such control and the optimum conditions that should be created from the point of view of service to the general public (Afolabi, Olajide & Omotayo, 2011; Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016). This is because, PRO contribute to air pollution and there has also been incidence of filling station explosions; according to World Health Organization (World Health Organization, 2004), more than 2.3 million lives and properties worth more

than US\$ 4.5 billion are lost to fire outbreaks associated to petroleum products mishandling (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016).

According to the National Geographic Society, the term spatial distribution refers to the way something is spread out or arranged over a geographic area. It is also the arrangement of a phenomenon across the earth surface. In geography, spatial distribution refers to how resources and activities, human demographics or features of the landscape are arranged across the surface of the earth (Reference.com, 2025). Geospatial analysis PRO in Yenagoa, Bayelsa tends to examine the distribution patterns of filling stations in Yenagoa capital city and its implication and effect on the environment as well as human health.

Mshelia *et al* (2015) assessed the environmental effects of petrol stations at close proximities to residential buildings in Maiduguri and Jere, Borno State (Ibrahim, Mohammed, & Abdullahi, 2023). They found that traffic accidents, traffic congestion and fire outbreak ranked very high from the perceptions of residents on the order of severity of dangers affecting them in relation to the distance between the petrol stations and the residential houses (Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016). They recommended planners should at all times assess possible hazards in planning and promote ways of avoiding or mitigating damage that might cause hazards, risk and vulnerability (Mshelia, *et al*, 2015; Taylor, Sichinsambwe & Chansa, 2016).

In many cities, urban growth has outpaced the ability of governments to build essential infrastructures; enact and enforce the legislation needed to make life in the city safe, rewarding and healthy (Olusegun, Olajide, & Omotayo, 2011). This urban growth has brought with it increasing use of automobiles, the need for fueling services and consequently, proliferation of filling stations (Olusegun, Olajide, & Omotayo, 2011). A number of PRO lacks the requisite safety measures in terms of layout, and where they are located. Filling stations are being built too close to each other in certain localities, and in residential areas against the guidelines for sitting such accident-prone facilities (Olusegun, Olajide, & Omotayo, 2011).

Since the PRO has spatial dimensions, it is expected that they are sited in an organized and sustainable manner (Olapeju, & Farotimi, 2017). It is however noticeable that despite the availability of standards regulating the location of PRO in Nigeria's urban centers, most petrol filling stations/PRO are still located in a manner that is chaotic and has the potentiality for hazards (Afolabi, Olajide & Omotayo, 2011; Olapeju, & Farotimi, 2017). They also observed that poor sitting of petrol filling stations' culminate in traffic congestion, pollution, and fire hazards (Olapeju, & Farotimi, 2017). There is therefore the need to carry out a geospatial analysis of PRO with the view to establishing its distributional pattern in the city of Yenagoa in Bayelsa State.

Materials and Method

Study Area

Yenagoa is currently the capital city of Bayelsa State with an estimated land area of about 706 km² (Ekin and Binaebi, 2018) as seen in Figure 1. It is bounded by Rivers State on the North and East, Delta State on the North West and West, Ogbia LGA on the South East and Southern Ijaw on the South west. Based on Eludoyin, Obafemi and Hardy (2017), the metropolis "lies along latitudes between 4° 48' 00" North and 5° 24' 10" East; and longitudes between 6° 12' 00" E and 6° 39' 30" E as seen in Figure 1.

The total population was 352,285 (National Population Commission [NPopC], 2010).

It has been asserted that Yenagoa metropolis have a tropical heavy rainfall climate (sub-equatorial climate) with lengthy and heavy rainfall seasons (over 250mm per annum) and very short dry season. The capital city has double rainfall maxima (June/July and September/October) with convectional type of rainfall.

In fact, it has been assumed that only the month of December and January are refers to as particularly dry season months in the city. Precipitation is at its highest in the month of September where on average approximately 370 mm of rain is observed (EaglesIsland Technologies, 2012). While the month of December sees an average in its driest month of the year where 20mm of rain on average is experienced (Iloeje 2007; EaglesIsland Technologies, 2012).

Figure 1. Bayelsa State Showing Yenagoa Local Government Area
 Source: Bayelsa State Office of the Surveyor General (2008)

The harmattan, which climatically influences many cities in West Africa, is less pronounced in the area, and temperature throughout the year in the city is relatively constant showing little variation throughout the year. Average temperature is typically between 27°C – 30°C in the city (EaglesIsland Technologies, 2012). Its relative humidity is very high. The area is situated in the salt water swamp forest vegetation. The swamps are made up of rapidly growing and regenerating mangrove plants with tangled mass of stems and roots, which are mostly aerial, because they tend to avoid as much water in the ground as possible (Iloeje 2007).

The area vegetation is characterized with tall, woody trees (white and red mangrove), evergreen trees with broad leaves. Trees like white mangrove, red mangrove and some raffia palms are found in the area (Iwena 2008). Although, the vegetation of this area is no longer in pristine state due to impact of man activities which has led to deforestation and deterioration of forest resources. Eludoyin *et al* (2017). Also reported that “like any other area in the Niger Delta, the vegetation is composed of mangrove forests, freshwater swamp and lowland rain forests” (Berezi, Obafemi, & Nwankwoala, 2019). The study area is located within the lower delta plain believed to have been formed during the Holocene of the quaternary period by the accumulation of sedimentary deposits (Eludoyin, O. S., Obafemi, A. A., & Hardy, T. (2017)). A typical relief of the area viewed from the 30 X 30 meters resolution United States Geological Surveys (USGS) digital elevation model (DEM) (Figure 1) shows that the lowest elevation ranged from 0 – 6meters while highest elevation ranged from 24 – 30 meters above mean sea level. The area is characterized by floodplains and is drained by Epie Creek, Orashi River and Ekole Creek. “Yenagoa Metropolis is surrounded by several swamps and back-swamps, which are linked to several other

tributaries and distributaries as it is the case in a typical deltaic setting. The water table here is very close to the ground surface varying in depth from 0 to 5 meters depending on the time of the year/season” (Bariweni and Amukali, 2017).

Traditionally, the Epie and Atissa villagers occupied the surrounding area of Yenagoa city before 1921. Then, their major socioeconomic occupation was mainly farming and fishing. At present, urban growth has ushered in several socioeconomic activities into the Yenagoa city, such as trading, transportation, exploration and oil production, as well as, craftsmanship and tourism (Dennis, 2013; EaglesIsland Technologies, 2012). Economic activities of Yenagoa city include, plastic rubber manufacturing, furniture, shop making and other informal sectors. Services include legal services, hospitality, medical, educational and engineering, services, etc (EaglesIsland Technologies, 2012).

Apparently, there is very few agricultural and agro-based business (logging and timber processes) existing in Yenagoa city. The main prevailing economic activities are small scale enterprises like consumer retailing, informal sectors, and artisanship and transportation business among others. Commerce, transport, industrial, administrative, and educational function are also common within the metropolis (Dennis, 2013).

Methodology

Data were collected through the use of a global positioning system (GPS). This enabled the researcher to take the coordinates of PRO within the study area. The coordinates of each station were taken and were later fed into the ArcGIS software for analysis of the distance between each filling station. Petroleum retail outlets (PRO), their operators/owners and residents living 100m close to PRO constituted the study population. The entire PRO was mapped in the study area. Simple random technique was adopted to select five (5) adult members of the households in residential buildings located 100m from PRO. Similarly, the survey instruments included field checklist, questionnaires and three (3) Garmin GPSMAP® 64st handheld global positioning systems (GPS) receivers. Semi-structured questionnaires were also deployed to elicit information concerning the effects of indiscriminate location of PRO near residential and built-up area in the study area.

Furthermore, field measurements were carried out using the GPS receivers to take the spatial coordinates of PRO within the study area. The coordinates of each station was taken at a spatial resolution of 3 meters and later exported into the Arc GIS 10.1 software for nearest neighbor analysis (NNA). The questionnaire were administered in line with the procedures described above in respective homes/shops of respondents living near the PRO. These questionnaire were administered during operating hours (8am – 6pm). Efforts were made to retrieve the questionnaire immediately after completion to avoid misplacement. However, non-returned questionnaires were inevitable and about 98.9% retrieval was achieved with the aid of three (3) trained research assistants.

The Nearest Neighbour Analysis (NNA) examines the distances between each point and closest point to it. The nearest neighbor analysis is a method of exploring patterns in locational data by comparing graphically the observed distribution functions of event-to-event or random point-to-event nearest to neighbor distances (Gandhile, & Petkar, 2018).

Results and Discussion

The importance of identification and mapping spatial phenomena in space cannot be over-emphasized. In this study, the spatial phenomenon was petroleum retail outlets (PRO) in Yenagoa Capital City with the view to building a geographic information systems (GIS) – based database to support planning and development decisions. It was discovered that that there are about 40 petroleum retail outlets (PRO) in

the study area. Three key players are involved in PROs business in the area namely government (NNPC), Major and Independent marketers. Out of the figure, 3 (7.5%) were operated by government, 35 representing about 87.5% were owned by Independent marketers while 2 representing 5% are owned by Major Marketers. Attribute data of respected PRO which contained the FID, Name, Address, Ownership and Geographic Coordinates of Petrol Filling Stations is presented in Appendix II while the spatial distribution of PRO is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Spatial Distribution of Petroleum Retail Outlets in Yenagoa Capital City
Source: Fieldwork (2024)

It is clear that the entire PRO is located along major axial roads in the capital city. Specifically, majority of the mapped petrol filling stations ($n = 27$, 67.5%) are concentrated along Isaac Borough road while 1 filling station representing 2.5% of the mapped filling stations is found in Sanni Abacha Expressway. Also, seven which represent 17.5% of the mapped PRO is found along Mbiama – Yenagoa road whereas, 5 (12.5%) of the mapped PRO is located along Imgbi street. Motorists and residents in areas with no PRO will need to travel longer distance in order to purchase petroleum related products for their domestic and commercial needs in other locations.

Determining the spatial patterns of phenomena in space is one of the core issues addressed by geographers and planners. The cardinal motivation is to support decision. Several methods used in determining the spatial patterns of phenomena are also available in literature. This study used the Nearest Neighbour Analysis (NNA) in determining the distributional pattern of PRO in Yenagoa Capital City. The NNA was computed using Average Nearest Neighbour tool in Spatial Statistics Extension of Arc Map 10.3 software. The results as seen in Figure 4 show that the Observed Mean Distance of PRO is 422.76meters while the Expected Mean Distance is 676.01meters.

However, the clustered pattern discovered in study also coincides with results found in other studies conducted elsewhere. Ogundahunsi (2014) while studying 50 PRO in Ilesa, Osun State, discovered a clustered pattern with NNA index of 0.16.

Figure 3. Nearest Neighbour Statistics of PRO in Yenagoa Capital City
Source: Computed from Field Survey, 2024

Where there are no regulations, laws and standards, there are bound to be chaos and confusion. In Nigeria, the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR) has the overall institutional responsibilities to grant approval for the construction and operation of PRO after full compliance to establish guidelines. In this study, proximity analysis discussed previously and executed using buffer tool in Arc GIS 10.3 was used to determine the filling station's compliance with the 2km radius stretch standard as specified by the DPR. A total of 40 buffers were created around the 40 PRO and each buffer assessed to determine the number of PRO found within it.

As seen in the figure 4, the extents of petrol retail outlets' compliance with 2km radius DPR standard were categorized for easy visualization. One to four PRO were classified as complied while others who

could not meet up the standard were reclassified as Low (5 – 7), Moderate (8 – 10) and High (11 PRO and above). In general, the buffer analysis indicate that majority of the PRO (n = 37, 92.5%) did not comply while 3 (7.5%) complied with the 2km radius standards as specified by DPR. The standard states that “the total number of stations within 2 km radius of the site should not be more than four (4) including the one under construction” (Adetunji, & Adejumobi, 2024).

Figure 4. Extent of Petrol Retail Outlets' Compliance with 2km Radius Standard

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Thus, Tamic (Nig.) Ltd, a PRO which is located along Isaac Boro Road have up to 12 retail outlets including itself located within 2km radius. Petrol retail outlets which have up to 10 retail outlets each, including itself located within 2km radius include Patcey Oil Nig. Ltd, Pet Oil & Gas and Unless God (found along Isaac Boro Road) as well as TAMIC and Ido Oil (situated along Mbiama – Yenagoa Road). Besides, PRO which have up to 9 retail outlets each, including itself located within 2km radius include Total, De-Arizona and Paudsiman filling stations (found along Mbiama – Yenagoa Road), Unless God, NNPC I, Jovero, Patcey Oil, Tadaerigha Ventures and Watgo Petroleum filling stations (situated along Isaac Boro Road) as well as Ido and Doncont Oil & Gas Nig. Ltd PRO located along Imgbi Street and Sanni Abacha Expressway respectively.

In addition, Emily Oil & Gas, Kofaben International I, Kobison Oil, Kofaben International II, South-South Oil & Gas and NNPC I stations, all clustering long Isaac Boro Road, each have 8 retail outlets including itself located within 2km radius. Ereboter, RSK Petroleum Reenter and a filling station with No Name all located along Imgbi Street in the capital city as well as Tonimas, Gamac and Bobele, found in Isaac Boro Road each, all have 7 retail outlets including itself located within 2km radius. Emitare (Nig.) Ltd and Eneni filling stations both situated along Isaac Boro Road and Sobaz Nig. Ltd found in Mbiama – Yenagoa Road each, all have 6 retail outlets including it located within 2km radius. Carol Oil, found along Mbiama – Yenagoa Road as well as NNPC I, Mobil and Otueyal, all situated along Isaac Boro Road, each have 5 retail outlets including itself located within 2km radius. Sobaz, PRO with No Name

and Danny Peace all situated along Isaac Boro Road, each have 1, 4 and 3 PRO respectively including itself located within 2km radius thus making them to be the only PRO that Complied with DPR standards.

Recommendations

The following recommendations become necessary. Appropriate sanctions should be meted on PRO operators/owners who have violated the DPR rules. These may range from withdrawal of operational license, stiffer financial fines, closure and/relocation among others. Also effective legislations and enforcement mechanism should be put in place by appropriate authority. Similarly, geospatial technologies which include remote sensing, GIS and GPS should be deployed in the assessment of spatial phenomena as it is capable of supporting policies and in making informed decision.

Conclusion

This paper attempt to investigate the geospatial analysis of petroleum retail outlets in Yenagoa metropolis, Bayelsa state, Nigeria. The importance of geospatial analysis of PRO in Yenagoa Metropolis cannot be over-emphasized especially with the increasing players and stakeholders within the downstream sector of petroleum industry. The capabilities of GIS, remote sensing and GPS have also proven its worth in spatial phenomena investigation, analyses and presentation to support decision. Non-compliance to established standards by operators is a serious threat to sustainable urban planning and management.

Petroleum retail outlets are highly environmentally responsive socio-economic venture. Situating an environmentally sensitive commercial and service activities in densely populated urban areas should be guided by planning principles and standards, expressed in either structure plans or land use development plans (Tah, 2017). Also, in the context of health, risk, safety as well as sustainable urban planning and environmental management, the culture of obedience, observance and conformity which connotes compliance to planning laws and standard of any development activity including PFSs on environment should be uncompromised and strictly adhered to.

All hands must therefore be on deck to checkmate indiscriminate sitting of PRO in metropolitan areas. Attitudinal changes, policies, public enlightenment and sensitization programmes as well as interventions need not only to be adequately prioritized but properly shifted and tailored in appropriate direction in order to achieve an orderly planned city space.

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